

Supplementary Table S1. Results from univariable analyses of herd-level risk factors for having high incidence of *Streptococcus dysgalactiae* subspecies *dysgalactiae* SDDS (case herds) compared to no detected SDDS (control herds), based on data from the Norwegian Herd Recording System and a farmer survey, in total 549 farms. Further multivariable analysis included freestalls only; the results are therefore presented separately for freestalls and tiestalls here.

Name of variable	Categories	Total (n=549) ^c		Tiestalls (n=184)		Freestalls (n=365)	
		Case (n=132)	Control (n=417)	Case (n=28)	Control (n=156)	Case (n=104)	Control (n=261)
Type of milking system (n (%)) ^{a,*}	Pipeline	28 (21)	156 (37)	28 (100)	156 (100)	n.a.	n.a.
	AMS	70 (53)	222 (53)	n.a.	n.a.	70 (67)	222 (85)
	Parlour	34 (26)	39 (9)	n.a.	n.a.	34 (33)	39 (15)
Herd size (mean, SD) ^{a,1}		39 (19)	35 (15)	25 (5)	25 (5)	42 (20)	42 (15)
SCC (mean, SD) ^{a,2}		132 (34)	125 (34)	115 (32)	120 (33)	136 (34)	129 (33)
Annual milk production/cow, mean (SD) ^a		8544 (963)	8450 (1033)	8043 (753)	8146 (1021)	8680 (972)	8632 (999)
Breeding index, mean (range) ^a							
Milk leakage		100.6 (94-106)	100.6 (93-105)	100.9 (95-106)	101 (93-106)	100.7 (94-105)	100.5 (94-105)
Milk flow		99.7 (93-104)	99.7 (93-107)	99.2 (93-104)	99.5 (93-106)	99.9 (94-104)	99.9 (95-107)
Mastitis		99.7 (87-104)	100.0 (94-112)	100.0 (95-104)	99.7 (94-104)	99.7 (87-104)	100.0 (94-106)
SCC		99.3 (92-104)	99.7 (92-107)	99.8 (92-104)	99.6 (93-107)	99.0 (94-104)	99.9 (92-106)
Kg concentrate used per 100 kg produced milk (mean (SD)) ^a		31 (5)	31 (5)	31 (4)	31 (4)	31 (5)	31 (5)
Vitamin/mineral supply is given to dry cows (n (%)) ^b	Yes	68 (52)	209 (50)	14 (50)	60 (39)	54 (52)	149 (57)
	No	63 (48)	205 (50)	14 (50)	94 (61)	49 (48)	111 (43)
Type of flooring in alleys (n (%)) ^{b,*}	Slatted	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	63 (61)	205 (79)
	Closed	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	37 (36)	48 (18)
	Other	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	4 (4)	8 (3)
Building year of the barn (n (%)) ^{b,*}	Before 2000	132 (100)	417 (100)	28 (100)	156 (100)	28 (26)	44 (17)
	2000-2010	36 (35)	130 (50)	0	0	36 (35)	130 (50)
	After 2010	40 (38)	87 (33)	0	0	40 (38)	87 (33)
Type of ventilation (n (%)) ^b	Closed/mechanical	112 (85)	351 (84)	27 (96)	27 (96)	85 (82)	200 (77)
	Open/natural	20 (15)	58 (14)	2 (1)	1 (4)	19 (18)	56 (21)
	Other/combinations	0 (0)	8 (2)	3 (2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (2)
Temperature in the barn (December to February) (n (%)) ^b	0-10°C	63 (48)	193 (47)	1 (4)	41 (27)	62 (60)	152 (59)
	11-15°C	50 (38)	184 (45)	16 (59)	96 (62)	34 (33)	88 (34)
	>15°C	7 (5)	13 (3)	4 (15)	9 (6)	4 (4)	4 (2)
	Adjusted according to outdoor temperature	33 (6)	23 (6)	6 (22)	8 (5)	3 (3)	15 (6)

Observes signs of high humidity in the barn during the winter (n (%)) ^b	Rarely	69 (52)	246 (60)	10 (36)	62 (40)	59 (57)	152 (59)
	Sometimes/often	63 (48)	167 (40)	18 (64)	94 (60)	45 (43)	105 (41)
Type of cubicle base (n (%))* ^b	Rubber mats	110 (84)	326 (78)	28 (100)	155 (99)	81 (80)	171 (67)
	Mattresses	21 (16)	86 (21)	0	0	21 (20)	86 (33)
Time used for drying off cows (n (%)) ^b	≤ 1 week	69 (53)	223 (54)	14 (50)	82 (53)	55 (53)	141 (55)
	1-2 weeks	52 (40)	161 (40)	13 (46)	68 (44)	39 (38)	93 (36)
	Abrupt	10 (8)	29 (7)	1 (4)	6 (4)	9 (9)	23 (9)
Where the cows are stalled during dry off (n (%)) ^b	In the milking department	58 (56)	135 (52)	n.a.	n.a.	58 (56)	135 (52)
	Calving/VIP pen	16 (15)	34 (13)	n.a.	n.a.	16 (15)	34 (13)
	Dry cow pen	30 (29)	92 (35)	n.a.	n.a.	30 (29)	92 (35)
Type of calving facilities (n (%)) ^b	Calving pen	85 (64)	190 (46)	n.a.	n.a.	85 (82)	190 (73)
	In the milking department	13 (10)	45 (11)	n.a.	n.a.	13 (13)	45 (17)
	Tiestall/outdoors/other	34 (26)	179 (43)	28 (100)	153 (100)	6 (6)	26 (10)
Yearly (or more often) service on the milking machine (n (%)) ^b	Yes	109 (83)	338 (82)	22 (79)	120 (78)	87 (84)	218 (84)
	No	22 (17)	76 (18)	6 (22)	34 (22)	16 (16)	42 (16)
Type of manure scraping (floor) (n (%)) ^b	Manual	27 (26)	78 (30)	n.a.	n.a.	27 (26)	78 (30)
	Robot scraper	35 (34)	120 (46)	n.a.	n.a.	35 (34)	120 (46)
	Mechanical scraper	39 (38)	58 (22)	n.a.	n.a.	39 (38)	58 (22)
	No manure scraping	3 (3)	4 (2)	n.a.	n.a.	3 (3)	4 (2)
Frequency of scraping/rebedding of cubicles (n (%)) ^b	Twice daily	85 (65)	243 (59)	6 (21)	52 (34)	79 (77)	191 (74)
	> Twice daily	41 (31)	142 (35)	22 (79)	99 (64)	19 (18)	43 (17)
	Once daily	4 (4)	26 (6)	0 (0)	3 (2)	5 (5)	23 (9)
Type of bedding material in cubicles (n (%)) ^{b,*}	Sawdust	121 (92)	365 (88)	28 (100)	145 (93)	93 (89)	220 (84)
	Other	6 (5)	16 (4)	0 (0)	5 (3)	6 (6)	11 (4)
	None	5 (4)	36 (9)	0 (0)	6 (4)	5 (5)	30 (11)
Hygienic focus (free stalls) (n (%)) ^{b,3}	Low	53 (51)	123 (47)	n.a.	n.a.	53 (51)	123 (47)
	High	51 (49)	138 (53)	n.a.	n.a.	51 (49)	138 (53)
Frequency of cleaning (removing biofilm) from water troughs (n (%)) ^b	Every day	12 (12)	21 (8)	n.a.	n.a.	12 (12)	21 (8)
	1-3 times/week	51 (50)	140 (54)	n.a.	n.a.	51 (50)	140 (54)
	Less often than once a week	40 (39)	100 (38)	n.a.	n.a.	40 (39)	100 (38)
Timing for introduction of heifers to the milking department (n (%)) ^{b,*}	<3 weeks before calving	34 (33)	73 (29)	n.a.	n.a.	34 (33)	73 (29)
	Week 3-6 before calving	45 (44)	142 (44)	n.a.	n.a.	45 (44)	142 (44)
	>6 weeks before calving	11 (11)	13 (5)	n.a.	n.a.	11 (11)	13 (5)

	After calving	12 (12)	28 (11)	n.a.	n.a.	12 (12)	28 (11)
Calves are fed with waste milk/high SCC milk (n (%)) ^b	Yes/Sometimes	104 (79)	305 (73)	23 (82)	114 (73)	81 (78)	191 (73)
	No	28 (21)	111 (27)	5 (18)	42 (27)	23 (22)	69 (27)
Pregnant heifers are housed with lactating cows (n (%)) ^b	No	94 (90)	232 (90)	n.a.	n.a.	94 (90)	232 (90)
	Yes	10 (10)	25 (10)	n.a.	n.a.	10 (10)	25 (10)
Total		132	417	28	156	104	261

*Univariable screening (freestalls only) $p < 0.2$

^aData obtained from the Norwegian Herd Recording system

^bData obtained from a farmer survey (questionnaire)

^cThe variables available for both tiestalls and freestalls had a number of missing values ranging from 0-5. Hence the sum does not agree with the total for all variables

¹Number of lactating cows

²Geometric mean bulk somatic cell count, 2018

³The variable was based on five statements regarding hygiene in freestalls: routines for clipping of udders, hygiene remarks from slaughterhouse, cleaning of rubber boots before walking in the feed alley, a general focus on keeping cows clean, and perceived problems with keeping the cows clean. E.g. "I always clean my rubber boots when moving from the animal pens to the feed alley" with the possible answers: Always agree-partly agree-disagree. The five statements were combined to one variable by creating a score for each statement (score 1 for low focus, score 2 for high focus). The median total hygiene score was used as a cut-off for low and high hygienic focus.